

Measles Epidemic in South India in 2024

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Abstract

Aims and background: Measles has made an unexpected comeback as a resurgent epidemic, with India among the worst-hit countries. The current study found that measles positive increased as a result of non-vaccination during the SARS-CoV-19 lockdown, which was a risk factor for the latest outbreak.

Materials and methods: This was a laboratory-based study conducted at the Microbiological Laboratory (MBL), Tamil Nadu, India. The study comprised patients aged one month to 83 years who were admitted to the hospital between January and March 2024. The samples collected from suspected patients were tested for measles-specific RTPCR using FTD Fever & Rash kits (Fast-track Diagnostics, Luxembourg). The clinical case definition of the World Health Organization was used to categorize Measles cases. The data were examined and presented in this research.

Results: There were 84 instances of measles positive for RTPCR out of 234, accounting for 35.89%. According to the study, the greatest positive rate for measles is 86.90% or higher in children aged one month to twelve years. The number of cases of measles peaked on January 24 (28.57%), February 27 (42.18%), and March 33 (38.37%). The SARS COVID-19 pandemic and its shutdown increased measles positive and non-vaccination.

Conclusion: This is an excellent time to boost not only our measles immunization program, but also our entire routine vaccination program; otherwise, cases of other vaccine-preventable diseases such as mumps, rubella, and whooping cough may grow in the coming years. This is a wake-up call to India's public health authorities to take the required steps to avoid vaccine-preventable diseases.

Keywords: Measles, Vaccination, RTPCR, Epidemiology, India

Introduction

Measles has returned unexpectedly worldwide, with the worst cases being in India (1). During the COVID-19 pandemic, measles cases in India plummeted to their lowest level in many years, with 5700 cases in 2021 and 5604 in 2020, compared to 30168 cases in 2015 (2). According to the CDC, the

United States and India had the largest number of cases in the world between April 2022 and September 2022, with Pakistan ranking seventh and the United States having 33 instances (3). The goal of eliminating measles by 2020 is still a pipe dream. In India, approximately 4 to 5 lakh babies are born each month. Even if we delay vaccination for a few months, the number of unvaccinated children is

staggering; almost twenty million children missed their measles vaccination injection in India alone in 2021 (4).

The rise in measles prevalence is thought to be the result of decreased vaccination coverage around the world, and this event has sparked public and scientific curiosity. In recent months, numerous Indian states have reported hundreds of measles outbreak cases, including Maharashtra and Kerala. As of December 12, 2022, Maharashtra had 199 confirmed cases of measles and 19 deaths. Cases have also increased in the states of Gujarat, Jharkhand, and Bihar. Thus, with vaccination rates down 42% since the pandemic began, increased burden on healthcare, and rising malnutrition, the measles situation threatens to spin out of control (7). According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), United States (US), India had the most instances in the globe between April 2022 and September 2022, followed by Pakistan in seventh place and the United States with 33 (8). The ambitious 2020 timetable for measles elimination remained a pipe dream. Each month, approximately four to five lakh children are born in India. Even if we missed vaccinating for a few months, the number of unprotected children is enormous; almost two crore children in India missed their measles vaccination in 2021 (4). The rise in measles prevalence is thought to be the result of decreased vaccination coverage around the world, and this event has sparked public and scientific curiosity. The present investigation reveals the current state of measles infection in the post-COVID-19 timeframe.

Measles infected nearly six million people worldwide, and 300 children (under the age of five) died each day. (9) India has the most frequent measles outbreaks in the world. According to recent studies, the majority (93%) of infections occur in children aged nine months to fifteen years; additionally, 172 government-confirmed outbreaks occurred between October 2021 and September 2022, with 12,589 cases officially confirmed (10). According to the National Family Health Survey - 5 (NFHS-5), 87.9% of children aged 12 to 23 months received their first dose of Measles-Containing Vaccine, while 31.9% of children aged 24 to 35 months received their second dose of the vaccine. The COVID-19 epidemic in 2020 has severely delayed the vaccination coverage region during the last few years. The Measles-Rubella (MR) 2020 initiative in India and the rest of South-East Asia have committed to controlling measles and rubella by 2023 (11).

Materials and methods

Microbiological Laboratory (MBL) twigs are found in several Indian states. Patients come to the MBL Centre from all throughout the district and nearby districts. Samples were collected from patients with Measles who visited the Pediatric and Medicine care units. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), measles is a highly communicable viral disease. It is easily transmitted when an infected person breathes, coughs, or sneezes. It can result in serious illness, complications, and even death (12). The samples were obtained 5-6 days after infection, following the onset of illness, but the exact date of sampling was not known for the majority of the patients. Approximately 2 mL of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)/blood was collected. The samples were analyzed for viral meningitis using FTD (Fast-track Diagnostics, Luxembourg) kits with Magnetic Induction Chamber (MIC) Real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR).

PCR

Extraction of RNA

Total nucleic acids were extracted from the samples using the QIAamp viral RNA Mini Kit with automated DNA extractor, QIAcube (Qiagen, Germany), following the manufacturer's procedure. During this time, both positive and negative controls for FTD viral meningitis were employed. The isolated RNA was then kept at -20 degrees Celsius.

Amplification

The total nucleic acids extracted were submitted to multiplex PCR with the Fast-track Diagnostics viral Meningitis panel. FTD Fever & Rash is an in vitro test that detects viral nucleic acid in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and blood samples for Measles, Enterovirus, Parvovirus B19, HHV6, HHV7, and VZV. Throughout this work, the RT-PCR assay was performed using the Mic Real-Time PCR System; IQ (Bio Molecular Systems®). The usual procedure for RT-PCR was used (13). A 25 µl reaction mixture with 10 µl of RNA, 2 µl primer, and components of a one-step RT-PCR kit (FTD) was used for the amplification test. The amplification process included the following steps: Reverse transcription at 42°C for 15 minutes; one cycle of initial reverse transcriptase denaturation and Hot Start Taq polymerase activation at 94°C for 3 minutes; 40 cycles of 8 seconds at 94°C and 34 seconds at 60°C (14). Each RT-PCR run includes both a positive and negative control kit. The results were evaluated using MIC PCR software and documented.

Figure 1. Month distribution of measles in 2024

Figure 2. Gender distribution of measles positivity in 2024

Figure 3. Age distribution of measles positivity in 2024

Figure 4. Age and gender distribution of measles positivity in 2024

Statistical analysis

The data was analyzed using the Epi Info version 6.03 program, specifically the Chi-square test for proportion and linear trend. Results were considered statistically significant at $P < 0.05$.

Results

During the investigation, a total of 234 samples were examined, with 84 (35.89%) testing positive for measles (Fig 1). Of the 234 cases tested (155 men, 79 females), 52 (33.5%) were males, whereas 32 (40.5%) were females (Fig 2). The overall rise in positive attitudes among females during the study period was determined to be statistically significant ($P = 0.6902$).

Of the 234 patients tested, 189 (80.76%) were under the age of 18, while 45 (19.29%) were over the age of 18. Among the Measles positives, 76 (90.47%) were children, whereas 8 (9.53%) were adults (Figure 3). The samples were taken from individuals aged 0-83, with an average age of 10 ± 2 years. The overall rise in measles positive among pediatric cases was not statistically significant, with $P = 0.9029$. Among the pediatric age groups, male positive was considerably higher in the 6-12 year age group than in the 1-5 year age group, and female positivity was significantly higher in the 1-5 year age group than in the 6-12 year age group, with a nonsignificant P value ($P = 0.2104$) (Figure 4). From the blood 59 (25.21%) and CSF 175 (74.78%) sample testing, it was determined that 64 people had meningitis and 20 had measles in their blood. Despite the presence of severe measles meningitis in four of the patients, there was no death during the research period due to quick diagnosis and appropriate therapeutic care. All patients with measles who developed problems were admitted, while the others were managed as outpatients.

Discussion

In this study, more male cases were tested positive than female cases; also, many of the positives were juvenile instances. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), unvaccinated (MMR - Measles, Mumps, and Rubella) children are at high risk of severe measles infection. During the study period, positive for measles increased steadily from January to March, particularly in pediatrics. A large number of positive cases were observed in children aged six to twelve years old; male newborns are especially vulnerable to measles infection, while toddlers and children are mostly affected, both male and female. Only infants and children (unvaccinated individuals) became infected, while adolescents and

adults (vaccinated people) had a low number of positive cases. Unawareness of taking the vaccine on time causes measles infection and, in some cases, meningitis. As the world in general, and India in particular, recovers from the SARS COVID-19 epidemic, measles virus reappears as a major cause of morbidity, accounting for a large proportion of hospital admissions. One of the primary causes of the increase in incidence is a low percentage of vaccine coverage.

Measles has the potential to be eradicated, but it remains a leading cause of death among children, particularly in poor countries such as India. It is one of the most contagious diseases, with over 90% secondary infection in vulnerable home contacts (15). Measles has joined the list of diseases that have re-emerged in recent years. Alarming outbreaks have begun in areas where measles was on the verge of being eradicated (10). Measles required 92-94% population coverage for herd immunity to work (16). Low vaccination rates have been ascribed to low transmission in affluent countries, as well as the COVID-19 epidemic, fear, and lockdown in high transmission areas like as India. In the current study, 84 of the 234, admissions made throughout the study period had measles as the predominant presenting illness. This study reveals an age prediction for children aged 1 month to 5 years, with 42 cases positive (50%). It is well known that maternal immunity drops after 9 months, making measles more likely. Bendale and colleagues reported similar findings in 2017, with 56.7% of children afflicted in the 1-5 year age range (9). One more. Babita and colleagues published a similar study in 2013 (14). However, the current study shows that 16.66% of positive cases occur in children under 9 months, which is a worrying trend. In terms of case distribution by month, the season began with 24 positive cases in January 2024, which climbed to 27 cases in February and 33 cases in March. In reaction to the measles outbreak, apart from the natural seasonal fall in the number of cases, widespread revaccination may have had a positive effect on lowering measles transmission. In the current investigation, 70% of all measles cases occurred in pediatricians who had not been vaccinated for measles, had only gotten a single dose of a measles-containing vaccine, or had no recorded proof of immunization. Only 21% of incidents occurred in children who had clearly received two doses of vaccination. According to Pustake and colleagues in 2018, India's overall coverage of Measles Containing Vaccine - 1 (MCV1) was 86%, and Measles Containing Vaccine - 2 (MCV2) was 73%; additionally, 13% of people did not receive their second dose of vaccine, and 14% of the population

did not receive a single dose of vaccine. India is the second most unvaccinated country for measles (17). Ratnesh and colleagues in 2022, towards the surveillance of measles infection in vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals, found that in 2018 - 41% unvaccinated were affected by measles; 2019 - 41%; 2020 - 32%; and in 2021 - 17% (unvaccinated) were infected, but 38% of people were infected after receiving both dosages (18). In 2023, Kirti Premabhai Mehta and colleagues noted that the majority of positive cases occurred in the late winter and spring seasons (December to April), with 28% of positive cases occurring in March and gradually decreasing in summer (19). Buhl and colleagues in 2022 and Yadav RM and colleagues in 2024 found that measles positivity was higher in unvaccinated males than in female measles positive patients (20, 21). It is unclear whether the latest measles outbreaks were caused by this disturbance or by the disease's usual epidemiological course.

Conclusion

Measles is a high-risk infection among unvaccinated youngsters and a re-emerging disease. It is familiar among children under the age of twelve. Children can be cured with proper treatment and diagnostics. In certain cases, the person who took both dosages was also infected with measles illness. To avoid transmission, the government must raise awareness of measles and implement steps prior to the winter season. Infection within the vaccinated population stimulates the development of new vaccines to effectively prevent measles. There is an urgent need to boost the measles and rubella vaccination program in the measles outbreak area, as well as overall routine immunization; otherwise, other vaccine-preventable diseases such as mumps, rubella, and whooping cough may resurface in the future years.

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